

PREPARATION OF COMPATIBILIZER FOR IMPROVEMENT OF MECHANICAL AND ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYCARBONATE/MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Poly(3-hexylthiophene)-*g*-polycaprolactone (P3HT-*g*-PCL) was synthesized and used as a compatibilizer for polycarbonate (PC)/MWCNT composites. Both FE-SEM and melt-state rheology show that MWCNTs are homogeneously dispersed in PC matrix when P3HT-*g*-PCL is added to PC/MWCNT composites. The mechanical and electrical properties of PC/MWCNT composites are dramatically improved when a small amount of the compatibilizer is added to PC/MWCNT composites.

Keywords: compatibilizer, polycarbonate/MWCNT composites, mechanical properties, electrical properties

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been considered as an ideal filler for polymer composites owing to their outstanding mechanical [1,2], electrical [3-6], and thermal properties [7], as well as their high aspect ratio. However, to effectively reinforce a matrix polymer with these outstanding properties of CNTs, two main issues have to be resolved: homogeneous dispersion of CNTs in matrix polymer and strong interfacial adhesion between CNTs and matrix polymer. These requirements can be realized by improving the compatibility between CNTs and matrix polymer. In this regard, a key issue in development of polymer/CNT composites is how to maximize the compatibility between CNTs and matrix polymer [8-10].

A considerable number of studies on improving the compatibility between CNTs and matrix polymer have been based on the covalent functionalization of CNTs [11-23]. In this approach, the surface of CNTs is chemically functionalized by introducing directly functional groups onto the surface of CNTs via 'grafting from' [11-17] or 'grafting to' method [18-20]. Although this approach is very effective to enhance the compatibility between CNTs and matrix polymer, it inevitably requires complicate chemical reactions for introducing functional groups on the surface of CNTs. Furthermore, it usually destroys the π -electron system of CNTs, which often results in detrimental effect on improvement in mechanical and electrical properties of the resultant polymer/CNT composites. Therefore, as an alternative, the use of compatibilizer which can non-covalently interact with CNTs has been attempted by

several research groups [3, 24-27]. In this approach, the surface of CNTs is non-covalently functionalized with a compatibilizer that is able to improve the interfacial property between CNTs and matrix polymer. Therefore, development of effective compatibilizer is essential for improving physical properties of polymer/CNT composites. For effective compatibilization, the compatibilizer should be designed to favorably interact with both CNTs and matrix polymer. One of promising candidates for compatibilizer would be a graft copolymer, if the backbone and graft of the copolymer could be designed to favorably interact with CNTs and matrix polymer, respectively.

With this in mind, we previously synthesized a new compatibilizer poly(3-hexylthiophene)-graft-poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) (P3HT-*g*-PMMA) and found that it was very effective to homogeneously disperse multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) in poly(styrene-*co*-acrylonitrile) (SAN) [28] or PMMA matrix [29], where P3HT backbone and PMMA graft interact favorably with MWCNT and SAN, respectively. Hence, it is natural that this concept can be applied to bisphenol A polycarbonate (PC)/CNT composites, if it is possible to prepare a graft copolymer in which the graft part is designed to be compatible with PC.

PC is one of the most important engineering plastics, and is widely used for laser optical data storage, optical fibers, membranes and substitute for metal owing to the special combination of properties, including excellent toughness, very good dimensional stability, transparency, and thermal stability. This wide range of applications of PC can be even further extended by incorporation of CNTs into PC because well-dispersed CNTs may enhance various mechanical and electrical properties.

In this study, we first synthesize a graft copolymer composed of P3HT backbone and poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) graft, where P3HT and PCL interact favorably with CNT and PC matrix, respectively [30]. Furthermore, to investigate the effect of the chain length of P3HT backbone on both the dispersion of MWCNT in PC matrix and the physical properties of PC/MWCNT composite, two P3HT-*g*-PCLs with different DP of P3HT but the same graft density of PCL are synthesized and their effectiveness as a compatibilizer for PC/MWCNT composite is examined in terms of the dispersion of MWCNT in PC matrix and the mechanical and electrical properties of PC/MWCNT composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

All reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich otherwise noted. 3-Thiopheneethanol (99%), 3-hexylthiophene (99+%), and iron chloride (FeCl₃) (97%) were used as received. Chloroform and toluene used as solvent were purchased from Daejung Chemicals & Metals and dried by distillation over CaH₂. ϵ -Caprolactone (99%) was distilled over CaH₂. MWCNT with a diameter range of 25~70 nm and PC with molecular weight of 35000 g/mol were supplied from Jeio Co. and Cheil industries, respectively, and they were used as received.

Copolymerization of 3-thiopheneethanol and 3-hexylthiophene

The overall synthetic route to P3HT-*g*-PCL is represented in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 1, P3HT backbone was synthesized by copolymerization of 3-thiopheneethanol and 3-hexylthiophene using FeCl₃ and chloroform as a catalyst and solvent, respectively. Two P3HTs with the different DP were synthesized by varying the

reaction time under the same reaction condition (see Supplementary Information for more detailed procedure). The feed ratio of 3-thiopheneethanol to 3-hexylthiophene was 5. The molecular characteristics of two P3HTs are listed in Table 1.

Synthesis of P3HT-g-PCL

The compatibilizer, P3HT-g-PCL, was synthesized by ring-opening polymerization of ϵ -caprolactone using P3HT as a macroinitiator, as represented in Figure 1. Toluene and tin(II) 2-ethylhexanoate were used as solvent and catalyst for polymerization, respectively. In this study, two P3HT-g-PCLs were synthesized from two P3HTs with different DP. The molecular characteristics of two P3HT-g-PCLs are listed in Table 1.

Preparation of PC/MWCNT/P3HT-g-PCL composite films

All of PC/MWCNT/P3HT-g-PCL composites with different loading of MWCNTs were prepared by solution blending in the presence of two different P3HT-g-PCLs (denoted by C30 and C50 in Table 1). A typical procedure of PC/MWCNT/C30 composite containing 0.5 wt % of MWCNT is as follows: A dispersion of 10 mg of C30 and 10 mg of MWCNTs in 20 ml of chloroform was sonicated for 1 h. The dispersed solution was then added to a solution containing 2 g of PC in 20 ml of chloroform. The mixture was sonicated for an additional 10 min and precipitated in excess methanol. The precipitate was collected by filtration and washed subsequently with methanol. The filter cake (PC/MWCNT/C30 composite) was dried at 30 °C under vacuum for 24 h. For comparison, PC/MWCNT composites without P3HT-g-PCL were also prepared under the same procedure.

Films of PC/MWCNT/C30 were prepared by solution casting: A solution of PC/MWCNT/C30 in chloroform was poured onto a glass plate and then a doctor blade was used to prepare a solution film. The solvent was slowly evaporated at room temperature for 6 h and then the film was thoroughly dried under high vacuum at 30 °C for 24 h. Films of PC/MWCNT composites were also prepared under the same procedure.

Measurements

The fracture surface of PC/MWCNT and PC/MWCNT/P3HT-g-PCL films was observed for analysis of dispersion of MWCNTs in PC matrix using a Jeol JSM-6330F field emission-scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), operated at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. The sample films for FE-SEM observation were ultramicrotomed with a diamond knife to obtain a smooth fracture surface.

Rheological properties of PC, PC/MWCNT, and PC/MWCNT/P3HT-g-PCL were measured in the melt state using an AR2000 (TA instrument) equipped with parallel plate geometry (25 mm in diameter) at 260 °C. A dynamic oscillation frequency sweep ranged from 0.1 to 100 rad/sec is applied to the sample. Small strain amplitude (1%) was applied to the sample to deform the sample within the linear viscoelastic range.

The tensile properties of PC, PC/MWCNT, and PC/MWCNT/P3HT-g-PCL films were measured with a universal testing machine (Instron-5543) under a 1 kN load cell at a constant cross-head speed of 3 mm/min. At least five specimens were tested for each sample, and the tensile properties are reported on average.

The resistivity of PC/MWCNT and PC/MWCNT/P3HT-*g*-PCL films was measured with an electrometer (Fluke, 34 dual display multimeter) using two-point probe method and converted to the electrical conductivity (σ) using the following relation $\sigma = 1/t dR$, where t , d , and R are the thickness, diameter, and resistivity of sample films, respectively. The dimension of sample films is 10 mm in diameter and 0.05 ~ 0.07 mm in thickness. At least five specimens were tested for each film sample, and the results are reported on average.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two P3HT-*g*-PCLs with the same graft density of PCL but different DP of P3HT are synthesized, and they are denoted as C30 and C50 in Table 1, respectively. Experimental details and characterization of two P3HT precursors and two P3HT-*g*-PCLs are represented in the Supplementary Information. Here, one thing to be noted is that the DP of PCL graft is controlled for two P3HT-*g*-PCLs to have nearly equal total mass of PCL graft.

The dispersion state of MWCNTs in PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 composites is first investigated by FE-SEM. Figure 2 shows FE-SEM images of the fracture surfaces of composite films containing 0.5 wt % and 1 wt % of MWCNT. As can be seen in Figure 2A, PC/MWCNT exhibits a severe aggregation and uneven distribution of MWCNTs in PC matrix. Unlike PC/MWCNT (Figure 2A), MWCNTs functionalized with C30 or C50 are homogeneously dispersed in PC matrix, as shown in Figures 2B and 2C, indicating that two P3HT-*g*-PCLs are good compatibilizers for PC/MWCNT composites. However, a closer examination of FE-SEM images shown in Figure 2 reveals that PC/MWCNT/C30 shows better dispersion of MWCNTs in PC matrix than PC/MWCNT/C50, indicating that the compatibilizer C30 with lower DP of P3HT is more effective to homogeneously disperse MWCNTs in PC matrix than the compatibilizer C50 with higher DP of P3HT.

The dispersion state of MWCNTs in PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 is also evaluated by measuring the melt-state rheology. Generally, a neat polymer shows the Newtonian liquid-like relaxation behavior at low frequencies, which is characterized by the following relation: $G' \propto \omega^\beta$, $\beta \sim 2.0$, where G' and ω are the storage modulus and frequency, respectively. This frequency dependence of G' at low frequencies is decreased as MWCNTs are incorporated into matrix polymer (i.e., $\beta < 2.0$), since MWCNTs incorporated into matrix polymer affect the relaxation behavior of matrix polymer [27, 31-35]. Furthermore, the MWCNTs incorporated into matrix polymer affect more significantly the relaxation behavior of matrix polymer as MWCNTs are more homogeneously dispersed in matrix polymer, which results in smaller value of β . Therefore, the dispersion state of MWCNTs in matrix polymer can be assessed from the decrease in β value at low frequencies. Figure 3 shows the frequency dependence of G' for neat PC, PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 with 0.5 wt % of MWCNTs, and the inset in Figure 3 shows the variation of β value for both PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50 as a function of the MWCNT content. As can be seen in Figure 3, the β value of PC/MWCNT is not significantly decreased compared to that of neat PC, indicating that MWCNTs do not significantly affect the relaxation behavior of PC matrix. This is due to the poor dispersion of MWCNTs in PC/MWCNT composite, as identified by FE-SEM

observation (see Figure 2A). On the other hand, the MWCNTs functionalized with C30 or C50 significantly change the relaxation behavior of PC matrix, as evidenced by a significant decrease in β value at low frequencies of PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50. This provides another evidence for better dispersion of MWCNTs in PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50 as compared to that in PC/MWCNT (see Figure 2B and 2C). The inset of Figure 3 shows that the β value of PC/MWCNT/C30 is smaller than PC/MWCNT/C50, indicating that MWCNTs functionalized with C30 are more homogeneously dispersed in PC matrix than MWCNT functionalized with C50, which is very consistent with FE-SEM observation.

Figure 4 shows the representative stress-strain curves of neat PC, PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 when 0.5 wt % of MWCNT is added to PC, and mechanical properties of neat PC, PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 are listed in Table 2. When the mechanical properties of PC/MWCNT are compared with those of neat PC, it reveals that the tensile strength, Young's modulus and elongation-at-break of PC/MWCNT are significantly decreased as compared to those of neat PC, as shown in Figure 4 and Table 2. This is attributed to poor dispersion of MWCNTs in PC/MWCNT and weak interfacial adhesion between MWCNTs and PC. However, the mechanical properties of composite are dramatically improved when the MWCNTs functionalized with C30 are incorporated into PC matrix, as can be seen in Figure 4 and Table 2. Figure 4 and Table 2 also shows that both the tensile strength and Young's modulus of PC/MWCNT/C50 are comparable to those of PC/MWCNT/C30 but the elongation-at-break of PC/MWCNT/C50 is significantly lower than that of PC/MWCNT/C30 and even than neat PC. This trend is more clearly seen when the tensile properties of composites are plotted as a function of the MWCNT content, as shown in Figure 5. The decrease in elongation-at-break of PC/MWCNT/C50 is attributed to some aggregated MWCNTs in PC matrix (see Figure 2C). Figure 5 also shows that the mechanical properties of PC/MWCNT/C30 show an optimum when 0.5 wt % of MWCNTs is added. Further increase of MWCNT content results in a decrease in mechanical properties of PC/MWCNT/C30. This is probably because some of MWCNTs are aggregated in PC matrix when the MWCNT content exceeds 1 wt%, as observed in FE-SEM images of Figure 2B.

The electrical conductivities of PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30, and PC/MWCNT/C50 were measured and the results are listed in Table 2. When the electrical conductivities of PC/MWCNT, PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50 are compared, it is realized that the electrical conductivity has an order of PC/MWCNT/C30 > PC/MWCNT/C50 > PC/MWCNT at the same loading of MWCNTs (1 wt%). This suggests that the electrical conductivity of composite is closely related to the dispersion of MWCNTs in polymer matrix. In other words, the better the dispersion of MWCNTs, the higher the electrical conductivity of polymer/MWCNT composites. It is also interesting to observe that the percolation threshold concentration becomes smaller as the dispersion of MWCNTs becomes better: the electrical conductivity of PC/MWCNT/C30 starts to increase at 0.5 wt% loading of MWCNTs while those of PC/MWCNT and PC/MWCNT/C50 start to increase at 1 wt% loading of MWCNTs. Here, it is worthy to note that the electrical conductivity of PC/MWCNT/C30 with 0.5 wt % MWCNTs is 5.4×10^{-6} S/cm, which corresponds to the conductivity level required for anti-static applications.

The above results lead us to conclude that P3HT-g-PCL with lower DP of P3HT is more effective to homogeneously disperse MWCNTs in PC matrix and to

improve the mechanical and electrical properties of PC/MWCNT composites. To elucidate the reason why P3HT-*g*-PCL with lower DP of P3HT is more effective to disperse MWCNTs homogeneously in PC matrix, the degree of π - π interaction between two P3HT-*g*-PCLs (C30 and C50) and MWCNTs in PC matrix is evaluated by using the fluorescence emission spectroscopy. Figure 6 shows the fluorescence emission spectra of two P3HT-*g*-PCLs (C30 and C50) and their PC composites (PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50) in chloroform solution after the solutions are irradiated at 420 nm corresponding to the excitation wavelength of P3HT-*g*-PCL. As can be seen in Figure 6, the degree of fluorescence quenching is more efficient in PC/MWCNT/C30 than in PC/MWCNT/C50, indicating that the π - π interaction between C50 and MWCNTs in PC matrix is not so effective as that between C30 and MWCNTs.

CONCLUSIONS

Two P3HT-*g*-PCLs with the same graft density of PCL but different DP of P3HT are synthesized and used as a compatibilizer for PC/MWCNT composites. Both FE-SEM and melt-state rheology reveal that P3HT-*g*-PCL with lower DP of P3HT is more effective to homogeneously disperse MWCNTs in PC matrix than that with higher DP of P3HT. As a result, the mechanical and electrical properties of composites are dramatically improved when P3HT-*g*-PCL with lower DP of P3HT is used as a compatibilizer for PC/MWCNT composites, while P3HT-*g*-PCL with higher DP of P3HT improves moderately mechanical and electrical properties. The ineffectiveness of P3HT-*g*-PCL with higher DP of P3HT as a compatibilizer arises from the fact that it weakly interacts with MWCNTs via π - π interaction, as evidenced by the fluorescence emission spectrum.

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Table 1. Molecular characteristics of the compatibilizer, P3HT-*g*-PCL

Samples	M_n of P3HT backbone (g/mol) ^a	m/n ^b	Number of PCL graft per chain	DP of PCL ^c
C30	31 000	9	18	150
C50	48 000	9	30	100

^a Determined by gel permeation chromatography.

^b The molar ratio of two monomers (m/n in Figure 1) in polythiophene backbone.

^c Determined by ¹H NMR.

Table 2. Mechanical and electrical properties of PC, PC/MWCNT, and PC/MWCNT/P3HT-*g*-PCL composite films

Samples	MWCNT content (wt %)	Young's modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Electrical conductivity (S/cm)
Neat PC	-	1477±43	41.4±1.3	60±10	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT ^a	0.1	1418±56	38.8±1.4	30±5	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT ^a	0.5	1314±65	33.3±1.8	5.2±1.4	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT ^a	1	1037±29	16.8±2.4	2.4±0.5	2.8×10 ⁻⁵
PC/MWCNT/C30	0.1	1794±46	52.0±2.0	80±10	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT/C30	0.5	2160±66	61.0±2.5	70±10	5.4×10 ⁻⁶
PC/MWCNT/C30	1	1953±73	52.3±1.6	40±20	1.1×10 ⁻²
PC/MWCNT/C50	0.1	1784±63	50.8±1.6	60±20	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT/C50	0.5	2122±20	55.4±2.3	20±10	10 ⁻¹⁵
PC/MWCNT/C50	1	1895±82	47.0±2.3	12±3	6.4×10 ⁻³

^a PC/MWCNT is prepared without P3HT-*g*-PCL.

Figure 1. The overall synthesis route of the compatibilizer, P3HT-*g*-PCL.

Figure 2. FE-SEM images of the fracture surface of (A) PC/MWCNT, (B) PC/MWCNT/C30, and (C) PC/MWCNT/C50. Left and right side images correspond to composites with 0.5 wt % and 1 wt % of MWCNTs, respectively. The white spots indicate MWCNTs.

Figure 3. Frequency dependence of the dynamic storage modulus (G') for neat PC (●), PC/MWCNT (▲), PC/MWCNT/C30 (◆), and PC/MWCNT/C50 (■). The amount of MWCNT in all composites is fixed at 0.5 wt %. The inset shows the variation of β value of both PC/MWCNT/C30 and PC/MWCNT/C50 with the MWCNT content. The β value is obtained by power-law fitting of G' for the five lowest frequencies.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of (a) neat PC, (b) PC/MWCNT, (c) PC/MWCNT/C30, and (d) PC/MWCNT/C50, where 0.5 wt % of MWCNTs is added to PC matrix.

Figure 5. (A) Young's modulus, (B) tensile strength, and (C) elongation at break of PC/MWCNT (\blacktriangle), PC/MWCNT/C30 (\bullet), and PC/MWCNT/C50 (\blacksquare) as a function of the MWCNT content.